

Improving Work Engagement Strengthened by Self Efficacy and Organizational Culture

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ABSTRACT

Employees' performance influences an organization's success; an organization will try to improve employee performance to achieve organizational goals; employees are an important factor. The success of an organization depends on the performance of its employees. This research analyzes the influence of self-efficacy and organizational culture on work engagement. Data analysis techniques use description analysis and regression analysis. Self-efficacy is formed from self-confidence, self-control, self-adjustment, self-effectiveness, and positive attitudes. Self-control is the biggest contribution to the formation of self-efficacy, reflected in remaining calm in the face of difficulties because you can rely on emotional abilities. Organizational culture is formed from involvement, consistency, adaptation, and mission. The greatest contribution to the formation of organizational culture is adaptation. This can be seen from the attitude of employees who always follow every change in organizational culture with full responsibility. Work engagement is formed from enthusiasm, dedication, and appreciation. The biggest contribution to forming work engagement is dedication, reflected in pride in the work done. Employee performance is formed from being service-oriented, accountable, competent, harmonious, and loyal. The greatest contribution to the formation of employee performance is competence, reflected in always improving one's competence to answer ever-changing challenges. Self-efficacy provides confidence and self-confidence in employees in their ability to be involved and contribute to work engagement, which can be seen in high work morale, enthusiasm for their work, and appreciation or focus in carrying out their work. Organizational culture guides employees in work behavior by providing an overview of the goals to be achieved together. Based on the research results, the following contributions are given. For the Pematang Regency Government, leaders of government agencies can pay attention to matters related to self-efficacy behavior, organizational culture, and job design to improve employee performance.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Human resources (HR) are the central force that drives the dynamics of an organization, the determining factor towards achieving organizational goals effectively and efficiently. Several factors greatly influence an organization's progress; in other words, a very important factor is having quality and reliable human resources in their field of work. Achieving a company's or organization's goals requires managing human resources effectively and efficiently. Human resource management does not only pay attention to the organization's interests but must also pay attention to employee needs and the demands of the wider community.

The performance of its employees influences the success of an organization. An organization will improve

employee performance in the hope that organizational goals can be achieved. In line with what Robbins (2006) and Luthans (2005) explained, employees are an important organizational factor. The success of an organization depends on the performance of its employees. In all jobs, employees determine success, so various efforts to improve organizational performance must start with improving employee performance. Employee performance can be evaluated and optimized through various employee performance assessment approaches. Therefore, understanding organizational behavior is very important to improve employee performance.

Employee performance is done by carrying out the employee's duties. Employee performance influences how

much they contribute to the organization, including quantity of output, quality of output, period of output, attendance at work, and cooperative attitude (Mathus & Jackson, 2001). So, employee performance is one of the keys to increasing the success of organizational goals. Government agencies, as organizations that serve the community, are also required to be able to adapt to the environment and developments that occur and be able to make changes. Achieving organizational goals requires employees to carry out their duties effectively, efficiently, productively, and professionally. This aims to ensure that the organization has quality human resources and, at the same time, is highly competitive in producing quality community services that align with community expectations.

In this case, employees carrying out public services are activities or a series of activities to fulfill service needs by statutory regulations for each community for goods, services, or administrative services provided by public service organizations. The community here is the beneficiary of public service employees, both directly and indirectly. Service standards are benchmarks used as guidelines for service delivery. The field of human resource management is interesting for further research. This can be seen by carrying out various studies, especially those related to employee performance in the form of empirical facts about HR performance with different approaches and study aspects. They consider humans the main driving force in organizations and have complex problems behaving in organizations.

Measuring employee performance in individual performance appraisal is a key element of performance management (Brudan, 2010). One of the problems with measuring employee performance is that it is not a static entity but an implemented process; therefore, there are several levels at which employee performance can be measured, such as input, output, and process. It is important to measure multidimensional aspects of employee performance to improve employee performance, which plays a dominant role in the system for better measuring and managing employee performance.

The concept of employee is very relevant for individuals and organizations. This is because employee performance is the most important factor for organizations to meet the needs of stakeholders. This reflects that an organization is the people in it and the people who shape the place (Schneider, 2008). In general, employee performance is an individual's ability to realize employee work goals, meet work expectations, and achieve work standards set by the organization (Viswesvaran, 2000). Koopmans et al. (2011) maintain that employee performance requires three definitions: First, performance must be defined in terms of behavior rather than outcomes. Second, employee performance only includes behavior relevant to organizational goals; third, employee performance is a multidimensional task, contextual, adaptive, and

counterproductive behavior. Task performance involves behavioral patterns directly supporting an organization's core technical processes (Van Scotter et al., 2000). Task performance includes a person's contribution to organizational performance and actions that are part of the formal reward system and fulfill the requirements specified in the job description (Tett et al., 2000).

This research aims to describe the variables of self-efficacy, organizational culture, and work engagement and to analyze the influence of self-efficacy and organizational culture on work engagement. The benefit of this research is that, theoretically, it can enrich human resource management literature, especially regarding the influence of self-efficacy, organizational culture, and job design on employee performance by mediating work engagement. The results of this research can be used as a reference for researchers interested in similar fields or related fields. Practical benefits are expected to benefit regional heads related to efforts to improve employee performance as public implementers who will satisfy the community.

Much employee performance research has been carried out on various organizational characteristics, including in public service agencies (local government) because employee performance ensures that employees provide the best work results. Thus, employee performance is an essential tool in managing human resources in government agencies and is related to improving community welfare. The best employee performance can be achieved if employees have dedicated work involvement, supported by the clarity of job descriptions, habits characteristic of an organization, and an employee's self-confidence in carrying out responsibilities in various situations.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Resource View Theory (RBV) was first put forward by Wernerfelt (1984) in his work entitled "A Resource-based View of the Firm." Resource View Theory is a theory that describes a company that can achieve competitive advantage by relying on resources so that it can direct the company to be continuously sustainable (Barney, 1986). The main approach of Resources Theory is understanding the relationship between resources, capabilities, competitive advantage, and profitability, especially understanding the mechanisms by which competitive advantage is maintained over time. Furthermore, Barney's (1991) "Firm Resources and Sustained Competitive Advantage" explains that company resources help companies improve the efficiency and effectiveness of company operations.

According to (Eduard L, 2011), RBV is also seen as the competitive ability of organizations with one another, which is a function of the uniqueness and value of an organization's resources and capabilities. The resource-based view (RBV) theory says that for a company to have a sustainable competitive advantage, an agency must have valuable, rare,

inimitable, non-substitutable resources that are different from others. Furthermore, Barney's (1991) "Firm Resources and Sustained Competitive Advantage" explains that company resources help companies improve the efficiency and effectiveness of company operations. Resources are defined as anything that can be considered a strength for an organization (Wernerfelt, 1984).

Resource-based View (RBV) theory discusses a company performance model focusing on controlling each resource and capability to achieve excellence for each company. RBV views that companies must pay attention to various resources different from all other companies. The resources in question are tangible and intangible assets that can be controlled by the company and used as a main strategy compared to other resources (Barney, 1991). Tangible resources, for example, are machines, medical equipment, land, buildings, and so on (Barney, 1991). Meanwhile, intangible resources include expertise, perception, culture, and so on (Ferreira & Ortiz, 2010).

Self-efficacy comes from Social Cognitive Theory (Bandura, 1997),

It is generally seen as a strong predictor/predictor of individual behavior; the point is that self-efficacy results from cognitive processes that occur in employees. Based on social cognitive theory, some experts have suggested that employees with creative self-efficacy beliefs will set more ambitious goals or subgoals than previous employee status, leading employees to engage in more creative actions Lucianetti, (2016).

Bandura (1997) first introduced the concept of self-efficacy. Self-efficacy is defined as the confidence an individual has in his ability to overcome difficult tasks. In essence, it is a belief in a person's ability to fulfill a task successfully. Self-efficacy is a person's belief in managing his behavior in carrying out tasks, overcoming obstacles, and achieving predetermined goals.

In this context, self-efficacy is defined as an individual's belief in his or her ability to achieve a goal or result (Tumasjan & Braun, 2012). Individuals with high self-efficacy tend to have high self-confidence to work actively to achieve goals (Bandura, 1997). It was further stated that self-efficacy is a person's evaluation of their ability or competence to carry out a task, achieve goals, or overcome obstacles Baron & Byrne, (2004).

Organizational culture is important for the implementation of employee duties. This is because organizational culture plays a role in giving identity to an organization Cheung et al., (2012). It was also explained that organizational culture can symbolize unspoken communication between employees (Graham, 2017). Organizational culture significantly influences how employees view the organization, responsibility, and commitment. Leaders influence subordinates directly through interactions and organizational culture (Chen, 2004).

Meanwhile, Luthans (2002) said that organizational culture is the norm and values that direct employee behavior in the organization. Employees will behave according to the prevailing culture so that their environment accepts them. Robbins (2001) further explained that organizational cultural norms and values refer to a system of shared meaning held by employees that differentiates the organization from others. I agree with other experts that organizational culture is a set of norms or values widely applied to an organization, Guiso et al., (2015). In more complete terms, organizational culture is a system of norms or values that are believed by all employees of an organization and which are studied, applied, and developed continuously, functioning as an adhesive system and can be used as a reference for behavior in the organization to achieve the company goals set by Guiso et al., (2015).

According to Nusatria (2011), engagement is a multidimensional idea. Employees can be emotionally, cognitively, or physically involved. Engagement occurs when someone is consciously aware or emotionally connected to another employee. Disengaged Employees, on the other hand, let go of themselves and their work tasks and withdraw consciously and emotionally (Mursatria, 2011).

Kahn (1990) stated that engagement is a construct that looks at employee differences and how much energy and dedication is given to work. Engagement has a multidimensional construct where engagement is both emotional, physical, and cognitive (Vibrayani, 2012). Work engagement is defined as a positive, satisfying, work-related state of mind characterized by enthusiasm, dedication, and appreciation Schaufeli et al., (2002)

Schaufelli et al. (2002) explain work engagement as the opposite of burnout, a condition where employees feel positive and satisfied. This motivational construct is characterized by the presence of vigor (spirit), dedication (dedication), and absorption (appreciation) in employees. Schaufeli (2004) developed engagement and defined work engagement as "a motivational, positive, fulfilling, work-related state of mind that is characterized by vigor, dedication, and absorption." work related to the mind is characterized by vigor, dedication, and absorption. Vigor is characterized by high energy during work, sincerity to put effort into a job, and perseverance even when faced with various difficulties (Schaufeli et al., 2004). A sense of enthusiasm, inspiration, pride, and challenge characterizes dedication. Dedication has a broader scope, referring to belief or cognitive states and affective Schaufeli et al. (2004). Absorption is characterized by full and deep concentration on work so that the work at hand feels enjoyable and is completed quickly.

3. RESEARCH METHODS

3.1 Research Design

Researchers used a quantitative design approach. The data collection process uses a perceptual approach, with respondents answering a list of statements in the questionnaire relating to self-efficacy, organizational culture, job design, and work engagement. The study will be carried out on the performance of civil servants in public service organizations or government agencies. The results of the analysis can be used to formulate strategies to improve existing resources, especially human resources or employees.

3.2 Research Location and Time

This research was conducted at the Pematang Rejang Regional Government, specifically the Regional Office. This selection is based on the reason that the Regional Service is the core function implementer (operating core), which carries out duties and functions as assistants to the Regional Head, which is filled by state civil servants, including Civil Servants in carrying out the function of regulating and managing according to the field of government affairs which is handed over to the regions to protect, serve, empower and prosper the community.

3.3 Population and Sample

The population used in this research comprised civil servants who worked in all Pematang Rejang Regional Service Offices, totaling 805 people. The population comprises civil servants whose work is assessed because each employee must be responsible. Determine the minimum sample size using the Slovin formula with the following details:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N (e)^2}$$

Keterangan:

n = Ukuran sampel

N = Ukuran populasi

e = Persentase kelonggaran ketelitian kesalahan pengambilan sampel yang masih bisa ditolerir; e=0,05

Thus, the number of samples is 163, which is suitable for SEM analysis. The sample size is based on the opinion of Hair et al. (2006); if the sample is large, it will be difficult to get the right model, and it is recommended that an appropriate sample size is between 100 and 200 respondents so that interpretation estimates can be used using SEM. Furthermore, the sampling technique uses a proportional sampling technique so that the number of samples will be represented proportionally in each regional service because each regional service has different services according to their duties and functions. The number of samples for each section was determined using proportional techniques and to determine the number of samples using the Slovin method.

3.4 Data Analysis Techniques

Descriptive analysis is intended to explain each description or characteristic of the variables studied: self-efficacy, organizational culture, job design, work engagement, and employee performance. The analysis technique used is descriptive statistics, namely frequency distribution table analysis, which explains the description of each variable and indicator using median and regression analysis.

4. RESEARCH RESULT

Regional offices as agencies to fulfill public service needs in Pematang Rejang are experiencing changes in numbers, and this is taking into account budget efficiency. In 2020, there were 19 regional services. There will be 17 regional services in 2021, namely by merging the Social Service with the Family Planning and Women's Empowerment Service, the Trade and Industry Service combined with the Cooperatives Service, and micro, small, and medium enterprises.

The descriptive analysis describes employee assessment tendencies toward research variables: self-efficacy, organizational culture, and work engagement. This process involves calculating the frequency distribution and average (mean) of the responses given by employees.

Based on the results, it can be seen that from the distribution of the self-efficacy variable, the first item, the self-confidence indicator (X1.1), the employees' answers remain calm when facing work difficulties because they can rely on their abilities. The highest perception response was that 76 employees (46.6%) said they agreed. Furthermore, 42 employees (25.8%) said they strongly agreed, 37 employees (22.7%) said they were neutral, eight employees (4.9%) said they disagreed, and no employees answered strongly disagree. The average score of 3.93 indicates that 163 employees agreed to remain calm in the face of work difficulties because they can rely on their abilities.

The self-efficacy variable, the second item, is an indicator of self-confidence (X1.1), the distribution of employee answers regarding employees who are ready to face problems at work, it was found that the majority of perceptions said they agreed, namely 96 employees (58.9%), then 38 employees (23.3%) said strongly agree, 21 employees (12.9%) said they were neutral, eight employees (4.9%) said they disagreed and no employees said they strongly disagreed. The average score of 4.01 indicates that 163 employees agreed and felt ready to face problems at work.

The average score of the self-confidence indicator is 3.97, meaning that employees agree that self-confidence impacts self-efficacy. The statement that employees are ready to face problems at work is given the highest perception when describing self-efficacy.

The first item's self-efficacy variable is an indicator of self-control (X1.2), the distribution of employee answers

regarding employees remaining calm when facing difficulties because they can rely on their emotional abilities. The largest response was 90 employees (55.2%), then 50 employees (30.7%) said they strongly agreed, 20 employees (12.3%) said they were neutral, three employees said they disagreed (1.8%), and no one answered strongly disagree. The average score of 4.14 indicates that 163 employees agree that employees remain calm when facing difficulties because they can rely on emotional abilities.

The self-efficacy variable, the second item, is an indicator of self-control (X1.2), the distribution of employees' answers about thanks to common sense, being able to handle unexpected situations, the majority of respondents agreed, namely 92 employees (56.4%), followed by 42 employees (25.8%) said they strongly agreed, 26 employees (16.0%) said they were neutral. Three (1.8%) of employees said they disagreed, and no employees strongly disagreed. The average score of 4.06 indicates that 163 employees agree that, thanks to common sense, they can handle unexpected situations.

The average score of the self-control indicator is 4.10, meaning that employees agree that self-control impacts self-efficacy. The statement of remaining calm when facing difficulties, because you can rely on emotions, gets the most response in describing self-efficacy.

The self-efficacy variable, the first item, is the indicator of self-adjustment (X1.3), the distribution of employees' answers about whatever they face at work and being ready to handle it. The highest perception was that they agreed, as many as 77 employees (47.2%), then 42 employees (25.8%) said strongly agree, 32 employees (19.6%) said they were neutral, 11 employees said they disagreed (6.7%), and one employee (0.6%) strongly disagreed. The average score of 3.90 indicates that 163 employees agree they are ready to handle whatever they face at work.

The self-efficacy variable, the second item, is an indicator of self-adjustment (X1.3), the distribution of employee answers about always being ready for new challenges in change, it was found that the majority of perceptions said they agreed, namely 89 employees (54.6%), then 47 employees (28.8%) said they strongly agreed, 15 employees (9.2%) said they were neutral, seven employees said they disagreed (4.3%). Five employees (3.1%) strongly disagreed. The average score of 4.01 indicates that 163 employees agree that employees are always ready for new challenges in change.

The average score of the self-adjustment indicator is 3.96, meaning that employees agree that self-adjustment impacts self-efficacy. The statement of always being ready for new challenges in change is most responded to when describing self-efficacy. The self-efficacy variable, the first item, indicates self-effectiveness (X1.4). The distribution of employee answers regarding whether they are confident they can achieve their goals. It was found that the majority of perceptions said they agreed, 72 employees (44.2%), then 46

employees (28.2%) said they strongly agreed, 34 employees (20.9%) said they were neutral, ten employees said they disagreed (6.1%), and one employee (0.6%) strongly disagreed. The average score of 3.93 indicates that 163 employees agreed they were confident they could achieve their goals.

The self-efficacy variable, the second item, is an indicator of self-effectiveness (X1.4), the distribution of employees' answers about having prepared well for the future of work, the majority of responses were that they agreed, namely 93 employees (57.1%), then 43 employees (26.4%) said strongly agree, 18 employees (11.0%) said they were neutral, eight employees said they disagreed (4.9%) and one employee (0.6%) strongly disagreed. The average score of 4.03 indicates that 163 employees agree that they have prepared well for the future of work.

The average score for the self-efficacy indicator is 3.98, indicating that employees agree that self-efficacy impacts self-efficacy. The statement of having prepared well for future work was most responded to when describing self-efficacy. The self-efficacy variable, the first item, is an indicator of positive attitude (X1.5), the distribution of employees' answers about facing problems at work, being able to find several solutions, the highest perception was that they agreed, 89 employees (54.6%), then 37 employees (22.7%) said they strongly agreed, 32 employees (19.6%) said they were neutral, five employees (3.1%) said they disagreed, and no employees said they strongly disagreed. The average score of 3.96 indicates that as many as 163 employees agree that they can find several solutions when facing problems at work.

The second item's self-efficacy variable indicates a positive attitude (X1.5). The distribution of employees' answers about always thinking positively about changes in work will be beneficial. It was found that most perceptions agreed, with 100 employees (61.3%), followed by 32 employees (19.6%).) said they strongly agreed, 26 employees (16.0%) said they were neutral, five employees (3.1%) said they disagreed, and no employees said they strongly disagreed. The average score of 3.97 indicates that 163 employees agree that always thinking positively about changes in work will be beneficial.

The average score for the positive attitude indicator is 3.97, indicating that employees agree that a positive attitude impacts self-efficacy. Thinking positively about changes in work will be the most useful response in describing self-efficacy. The average self-efficacy score is 3.99, meaning that employees agree that self-efficacy is formed from self-confidence, self-control, self-adjustment, self-effectiveness, and a positive attitude. The biggest contribution to the formation of self-efficacy is self-control, with a value of 4.11, reflected in the attitude of remaining calm in the face of difficulties because you can rely on emotional abilities 4.16. This value means that employees will respond calmly to

problems, challenges, or difficulties in carrying out their duties.

Based on the organizational culture variable, the first item indicates involvement (X2.1) from the distribution of employees' answers. The organization empowers its employees to achieve goals. The highest perception was found to agree with 74 employees (45.4%), followed by 44 employees (27, 0%) who said they were neutral, 30 employees (16.4%) who said they strongly agreed, and 14 employees (8.6%) who said they disagreed. One employee (0.6%) answered strongly disagree. The average score of 3.73 indicates that 163 employees agree that the organization empowers its employees to achieve goals.

The organizational culture variable, the second item, is an indicator of involvement (X2.1), the distribution of employee answers regarding employees working together with a team. It was found that the majority of perceptions stated that they agreed, namely 89 employees (54.6%), then 35 employees (21.5%) said they were neutral, 30 employees (18.4%) said they strongly agreed, eight employees (4.9%) said they disagreed and one employee who said they strongly disagreed (0.6%). The average score of 3.85 indicates that 163 employees agree that they feel like they are working with a team.

The average score for the involvement indicator is 3.78, meaning that employees agree that involvement impacts organizational culture, and employees' statements about working together with teams are given the highest perception in describing organizational culture. The organizational culture variable, the first item, is the consistency indicator (X2.2), the distribution of employee answers about being consistent with what has become a commitment. The most common perception was that 72 employees (44.2%) agreed, then 50 employees (30.7%) said they strongly agreed. Thirty-nine employees (23.9%) said they were neutral, two (1.2%) employees said they disagreed, and none answered strongly disagree. The average score of 4.04 indicates that 163 employees agree that employees are consistent with what they have committed.

The organizational culture variable, the second item, is the consistency indicator (X2.2), the distribution of employees' answers about not easily changing in their determination to achieve organizational goals. It was found that the majority of perceptions stated that they agreed, namely 88 employees (54.0%), followed by 42 employees (25.8%) who said they were neutral, and 31 employees (19.0%) who said they strongly agreed. Two or (1.2%) of employees said they disagreed. There were no employees who said they strongly disagreed. The average score of 3.90 indicates that 163 employees agree they stay the same in their determination to achieve organizational goals.

A consistency indicator score of 3.97 means that employees agree that consistency impacts organizational culture. Statements consistent with what has become the

commitment most responded to in describing organizational culture. The organizational culture variable, the first item, is an indicator of adaptation (X2.3). Distribution of employee answers about always following changes in organizational culture with full responsibility, it was found that the largest perception was that 83 employees agreed (50.9%), then 49 employees (30.1%) said they strongly agreed, 29 employees (17.8%) said they were neutral, two employees said they disagreed (1.2%). There were no employees who said they strongly disagreed. The average score of 4.09 indicates that 163 employees agree to always follow any changes in organizational culture with full responsibility.

The second item of the organizational culture variable is an indicator of adaptation (X2.3). The distribution of employee answers regarding work is by the work behavior guidelines, with the majority of perceptions saying they agree, namely 80 employees (49.1%), then 48 employees (29.4%) say they strongly agree, 30 employees (18.4%) say neutral, five employees said they disagreed (3.1%). There were no employees who answered that they strongly disagreed. The average score of 4.04 indicates that 163 employees agree that employees work by existing work behavior guidelines.

The average score for the adaptation indicator is 4.07, meaning that employees agree that adaptation impacts organizational culture. The statement always follows every change in organizational culture with full responsibility. Most responded by describing organizational culture. Variable The first item of organizational culture is the mission indicator (X2.4). The distribution of employee answers about whether work is by the organization's vision and mission found that the majority of perceptions were agreed: 82 employees (50.3%), then 42 employees (25.8%) said they were neutral, and 39 (23.90) answered strongly agree, no some employees answered neither agree nor strongly disagree. The average score of 3.98 indicated that 163 employees agreed that their work was to the organization's vision and mission.

The mission indicator (X2.4) is the organizational culture variable's second item. Employee answers about work are distributed by how to achieve the mission. It was found that the majority of perceptions said they agreed, namely 100 employees (61.3%), then 30 employees (18.4%) said they were neutral, 26 employees (16.0%) said they strongly agreed, seven employees (4.3%) said they disagreed, and no one answered that they strongly disagreed. The average score of 3.88 indicates that 163 employees agree that their work is by how to achieve the mission.

The average score of the mission indicator is 3.93, indicating that employees agree that the mission impacts organizational culture. The statement that work is by the organization's mission is the most responded to when describing the mission. The average organizational culture score is 3.94, meaning employees agree that organizational culture is formed from involvement, consistency, adaptation,

and mission. The biggest response to the formation of organizational culture is adaptation, with a value of 4.07, which is reflected in always following every change in organizational culture with full responsibility, with a value of 4.09. This value means that employees will continue to follow or adapt to all regulatory changes, whether changes originating from the central or regional level.

Based on the results of Work Engagement, from the work engagement variable, the first item is the enthusiasm indicator (Y1.1), the distribution of answers that employees have the ambition to complete the work according to the target. It was found that the highest perception was that they agreed, 63 employees (38.7%), followed by 56 employees (34.3%) said they were neutral, 38 employees (23.3%) said they strongly agreed, six employees (3.7%) said they disagreed, and no employees answered strongly disagree. The average score of 3.81 indicates that 163 employees agree they have the ambition to complete the work according to the target.

The second work engagement variable indicates enthusiasm (Y1.1), the distribution of employee answers about employees having energy at work. The results showed that the majority of responses stated agree, namely 101 employees (62.0%), then 34 employees (20.9%) said they strongly agreed, 23 employees (14.1%) said they were neutral, five employees (3.1%) said they disagreed, and no employees said they strongly disagreed. The average score of 4.00 indicates that 163 employees agree they have energy at work.

The average score of the enthusiasm indicator is 3.91, meaning that employees agree that variation impacts work engagement, the statement having energy at work gives the highest response in describing employee enthusiasm for work.

The work engagement variable, the first item, indicates dedication (Y1.2). Distribution of employee answers regarding enthusiasm in carrying out work, it was found that 94 employees (57.7%) said they agreed, then 41 employees (25.2%) said they strongly agreed, 25 employees (15.3%) said they were neutral, and employees whom three employees (1.8%) said they disagreed. No employees answered that they strongly disagreed. The average score of 4.06 indicates that 163 employees agree that having high enthusiasm in carrying out work will also result in high work involvement.

The work engagement variable, the second item, indicates dedication (Y1.2). The distribution of employee answers about being proud of the work they do received the highest perception of agreeing, namely 111 employees (68.1%), then 35 employees (21.5%) said they strongly agreed, and 14 employees (8.6%) said they were neutral. Three (1.8%) of employees said they disagreed, and no employees strongly disagreed. The average score of 4.09

indicates that 163 employees agree they are proud of their work, which is necessary to be fully involved in their duties.

The average score for the dedication indicator is 4.09, meaning that employees agree that dedication impacts work engagement. The statement that employees have energy at work is most responded to in describing work engagement. This indicates that dedication is a strong capital asset for employees. The work engagement variable, the first item, is an indicator of appreciation (Y1.3). Distribution of employees' answers regarding being diligent in carrying out work, it was found that the majority of perceptions stated that they agreed, 88 employees (54.0%), then 51 employees (31.2%) said they were neutral, 22 employees (13.5%) said they strongly agreed, employees who said two employees (1.2%) disagreed and no employees said they strongly disagreed. The average score of 3.80 indicates that 163 employees agreed to carry out their work diligently.

The work engagement variable, the second item, is an indicator of appreciation (Y1.3), the distribution of employee answers about concentrating while working, it was found that the majority of people agreed, namely 110 employees (67.5%), then 24 employees (14.7%) stated that strongly agree, 24 employees (14.7%) said they were neutral, five employees (3.1%) said they disagreed. There were no employees who answered strongly disagree. The average score of 3.93 indicates that 163 employees agree that they always concentrate when working.

The average score for the appreciation indicator is 3.86, meaning that employees agree that appreciation impacts work engagement. Statement of always concentrating on work. Most responded by describing work engagement. The average work engagement score is 3.95, meaning employees agree that work engagement is formed from enthusiasm, dedication, and appreciation. The biggest perception in forming work engagement is dedication, with a score of 4.07, reflected in being proud of the work done, with a score of 4.09. This value means that employees are always proud of their work and will continue to have a career in this job.

5. DISCUSSION

Based on research results, self-efficacy is formed from self-confidence, self-control, self-adjustment, self-efficacy, and positive attitudes. The greatest contribution to the formation of self-efficacy can be seen in employees' emotional control, reflected in their attitude of remaining calm in the face of difficulties in various changing conditions at work. This shows that employees with good self-control are equipped with high self-confidence so that they will be calm about all work problems, challenges presented, and obstacles they will face in carrying out their community service duties with various characters and diverse backgrounds. The results of this research are, as stated by Rigoti (2008), regarding things that need to be considered in employee self-efficacy.

Based on the results, Self-efficacy research is related to work engagement, a state of self-efficacy that shows the biggest role in increasing work engagement, namely the need for self-control, reflected in remaining calm in the face of difficulties because you can rely on your emotional abilities. Employees must adjust existing work standards or targets to carry out their duties. Performance assessment standards have changed several times and require quick adjustments. This fast adjustment requires a high level of trust and self-confidence so that you can get involved in completing the work. Employees who do not have work engagement tend not to be able to work optimally, feel less enthusiastic, less challenging, and lack meaning to their work. This is where self-efficacy is needed so that employees will have confidence in their ability to be involved and contribute to work optimally. The results of this research support Chan et al. (2020), Nusanmas (2020), Alessandro et al. (2015), and Orgambidez et al. al. (2020), who found that self-efficacy influences work engagement.

According to research results, organizational culture in an agency impacts work engagement or full involvement in employee roles. The component of organizational culture that shows the greatest perception of increasing work engagement is adaptation, which can be shown from the demand to adjust the rules of work behavior values quickly. Work guidelines are needed as a reference for carrying out tasks. One form of guidance is the values and norms in the organizational culture, which are used as direction for employee behavior at work. Clarity about the values set will make it easier for every employee to implement every change condition so that they will work with more enthusiasm, high dedication, and focus. The results of this research support Uhunoma et al. (2020), who found that organizational culture influences work engagement.

Self-efficacy, organizational culture, and job design play an important role in realizing employees who will be maximally involved in work or work engagement, with organizational culture making the biggest contribution or, in this case, the most dominant. Self-efficacy, organizational culture, and job design relate to work engagement. This is to the theory that self-efficacy, organizational culture, and job design can increase employee involvement in their work. Employees with high self-confidence who work in a supportive work environment and are satisfied with the design of their work will feel more motivated, committed, and dedicated to carrying out their duties.

One theory that states that self-efficacy, organizational culture, and job design can increase employee involvement is the work engagement theory developed by Schaufeli and Bakker (2004). This theory proposes that work engagement is a positive psychological state characterized by vigor, dedication, and absorption. Vigor is full of energy and enthusiasm that employees have when working. Dedication is employees' sense of pride, enthusiasm, and challenge

towards their work. Absorption is the full involvement, concentration, appreciation, and perseverance experienced by employees while working. According to this theory, self-efficacy, organizational culture, and job design are several factors included in job resources. These are aspects of work that can help employees achieve work goals, reduce work demands, and stimulate growth and development. Job resources can increase work engagement in two ways, namely through the motivational process and the health impairment process. The motivational process is when job resources increase engagement by meeting employees' basic psychological needs, such as autonomy, competence, and relatedness. The health impairment process is when job resources increase engagement by reducing work stress and improving employee health (Mazzetti et al., 2023).

Self-efficacy shows employees' confidence in their ability to complete public sector work tasks, which have many challenges due to the diversity of conditions in the community using services and regional situations well. Self-efficacy can increase work engagement by increasing job competency, self-confidence, and employee motivation. Organizational culture is the implementation of values, norms, and behavior shared by employees in the workplace. Organizational culture can increase work engagement by creating a positive, supportive, harmonious work atmosphere and clarity of mission. Job design clarifies how the agency organizes employee duties, responsibilities, and authority. Job design can increase work engagement by providing variations in task completion, a clear identity of each job, the significance of roles and tasks, and autonomy of approach in completing employee work.

6. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the research results, self-efficacy is formed from self-confidence, self-control, self-adjustment, self-effectiveness, and a positive attitude. Self-control is the biggest contribution to the formation of self-efficacy, which is reflected in remaining calm in the face of difficulties because you can rely on emotional abilities. Organizational culture is formed from involvement, consistency, adaptation, and mission. The greatest contribution to the formation of organizational culture is adaptation. This can be seen from the attitude of employees who always follow every change in organizational culture with full responsibility. Work engagement is formed from enthusiasm, dedication, and appreciation. The biggest contribution to the formation of work engagement is dedication, reflected in pride in the work done. Employee performance is formed from being service-oriented, accountable, competent, harmonious, and loyal. The greatest contribution to the formation of employee performance is competence, reflected in always improving one's competence to answer ever-changing challenges.

Self-efficacy provides employees confidence in their ability to be involved and contribute to work engagement,

which can be seen in high work morale, enthusiasm for their work, and appreciation or focus in carrying out their work. Self-efficacy significantly contributes to employees' readiness to face various obstacles at work, especially in contributing to their work involvement so that they remain enthusiastic and proud of their work and enjoy it more fully. Organizational culture guides employees in work behavior by providing an overview of the goals to be achieved together. Changes in the provisions of organizational culture will impact employee involvement in jointly contributing to each employee to the organization.

Based on the research results and conclusions that have been presented, suggestions can be made for the Pematang Regency government to pay attention to matters related to self-efficacy behavior, organizational culture, and job design to improve employee performance by including these work behaviors in assessing employee performance, because they have been proven to play a role. In improving employee performance with the following details, namely Self Efficacy should be further improved in the aspect of social support, namely being able to understand the situation of the work environment, training that will increase self-confidence in completing tasks, especially those related to readiness to face any conditions in work, good conditions that meet expectations or that are not so that they will remain calm to respond to all challenges which will increase comfort at work and always be motivated.

While maintaining consistent and effective communication from employees, organizational culture will help achieve the mission, and employee involvement at every level of work will be a form of employee empowerment so that a supportive work environment can quickly achieve organizational goals. This situation will be able to produce more varied alternative solutions to problems faced at work. A strong organizational culture reflects the implementation of all employees' shared values.

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